

HyDelta 3

WP4b – Digitalization: decentralized hydrogen feed-in

D4b.2 – Optimal sensor placement strategies for monitoring the dynamic pressure of gas networks

Status: FINAL

Document summary

Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Ryvo Octaviano, Demetris Palochis, Huib Blokland, Jonah Poort
Affiliation	TNO
Email address	ryvo.octaviano@tno.nl

Document history

Version	Date	Author	Affiliation	Summary of main changes
1	07-Oct-2024	Ryvo Octaviano	TNO	First version for EAG review
2	23-Oct-2024	Ryvo Octaviano	TNO	Include feedback and revision from EAG. Ready for Supervisory Group review
3	28-Nov-2024	Ryvo Octaviano	TNO	Include feedback from SG review and finalize

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
RE	Restricted to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project partners including Expert Assessment Group External entity with whom a Non-Disclosure Agreement exists 	

Document review

Partner	Name
Stedin	Iman Pishbin, Niek van den Bogaart
Enexis	Jeanine Stassen, Ruud Busscher
Alliander	Reon Baars
Coteq	Jerry Palmers
NBNL, Gasunie, Kiwa, DNV, TNO, NEC	HyDelta Supervisory Group

Executive summary

Changes in the operation of the future Dutch energy system bring challenges for the operation of the distribution networks. To connect local feeder, the pressure and flow in the gas network need to be regulated more actively. One of the challenges will be to accurately monitor the network with a limited number of sensors.

Optimal pressure sensor placement is performed with two methods. The first method is a list of criteria established by DSOs for finding critical locations, i.e. practical rules. The purpose of the practical rules is to assess extreme scenarios and the topology of the assets in the network and identify locations that can give a good indication of how close the network is to its capacity limit. The second method is a smart sensor placement algorithm which aims to reduce uncertainty (due to uncertainties in the input data for simulation tools) in the pressure values from the gas network model. The algorithm is capable of finding the optimal pressure sensor locations for minimum model-induced errors in the pressure values.

Two research questions were answered:

1. Realtime measurement is a pre-requisite for control: what is the optimal location for placing flow and pressure sensors to understand the system behaviour?
2. How can the combination of monitoring, simulation and control improve the operation of future gas networks?

Sensor placement with the practical rules provided by the DSOs and with the smart sensor placement algorithm, Astraia.

The activity focuses on finding the critical locations for pressure sensors in the domestic network of Uden-Boekel by employing the two methods and potentially combining the results into one optimal sensor placement. By definition, the practical rules and the smart algorithm have different objectives to achieve. Therefore, a combination of the two methods is proposed.

For the current case study, the performance of the pressure monitoring is measured as the standard deviation in the pressure values. The standard deviation comes from simulating random consumption variations and brings uncertainty to the monitored pressure values. Simulations were performed by TNO with Aurora, a validated gas network model that accurately estimated pressure, flow and gas quality in gas grids. The results of 1000 simulations with random variations were the input for Astraia, an optimization algorithm for sensor placement, which performed the optimization of 10 pressure sensor locations.

The simulations and sensor placement were performed on part of the 8-bar distribution network operated by Enexis. The network covers the municipalities of Uden and Boekel. Here is a list of the scenarios for placement of 10 pressure sensors (4 sensors from practical rules and 6 sensors from the optimal sensor algorithm).

Scenarios:

1. Base case: 10 pressure sensors placement only with the Astraia optimal sensor placement algorithm.
2. Practical rule 1 and optimal sensor placement algorithm. Practical rule 1 considers the district stations with the highest flow rates as critical locations.
3. Practical rule 2 and optimal sensor placement algorithm. Practical rule 2 considers the district stations at the lowest pressure as critical locations.

4. Practical rule 3 and optimal sensor placement algorithm. Practical rule 3 considers as critical, the station which are the longest distance from the supplier. For this rule, the distances to all of the three suppliers were estimated and examined for the implementation of the rule.

By performing the activity and analysing all of the scenarios, three main points were concluded.

The effect of pressure sensors placed by the practical rules was slightly lower than with Astraia.

Comparing 4 pressure sensors placed by Astraia and the practical rules, Astraia demonstrated the most decrease in the total pressure uncertainty in the network by 55%. Practical rule 1 showed a slightly smaller decrease of total pressure uncertainty at 46% decrease. Practical rule 2 and 3 has a decrease of 14% and 35% respectively.

The combination of the methods should be the most beneficial for the effective monitoring of the gas network.

Astraia was able to take pressure sensors placed by one of the practical rules and find additional locations of pressure sensors. The combination of practical rules and Astraia had a similar decrease in the total pressure uncertainty.

Depending on each use case, the critical locations given by the practical rules may be the minimum locations with pressure sensors. The implementation of Astraia and the placement of additional pressure sensors at optimal locations, is ensuring that the final pressure uncertainty in the network is within the limits.

Without pressure sensors in the network, the uncertainty in pressure levels can be too high for proper control of the grid.

Regarding the effective control of the pressure setpoint at the GOS in a gas network, there should be a desired pressure accuracy. In use cases where local feeders are in small distance from each other, the minimum accuracy for control can be in the order of magnitude of 0,5 bar. Therefore, the network may be monitored with an equal or higher accuracy. This means, that in the case of Uden-Boekel, the acceptable pressure uncertainty should be reduced significantly.

General conclusion

Controlling the outlet pressure of a decentralised hydrogen feeder can increase the feed-in capacity of this feeder. To do this, the pressures in the network need to be measured with a certain accuracy. A combination of a gas network simulator and sensors provides more insight into the pressures in the network than using a simulator or sensors alone. It has been demonstrated that the pressure uncertainty from the gas network model (due to uncertainty in the demand data) can be simulated and reduced by using sensors. The application of practical rules with Astraia can find the optimal pressure sensor locations to achieve acceptable pressure uncertainty levels. This allows the pressures of the feeders to be actively controlled, increasing the total feed-in capacity and reducing the need for shutdowns or boosters to manage surplus production.

Samenvatting

Veranderingen in de werking van het toekomstige Nederlandse energiesysteem brengen uitdagingen met zich mee voor de exploitatie van het distributienetwerk. Om lokale invoeders aan te kunnen sluiten, moeten druk en stroming in het gasnetwerk actiever worden geregeld. Een van de uitdagingen zal zijn om het netwerk nauwkeurig te monitoren met een beperkt aantal sensoren.

Optimale plaatsing van druksensoren wordt uitgevoerd met twee methoden. De eerste methode is een lijst met criteria die door DSO's zijn opgesteld om kritieke locaties te vinden, d.w.z. praktische regels. Het doel van de praktische regels is om extreme scenario's en de topologie van de assets in het netwerk te beoordelen en locaties te identificeren die een goede indicatie kunnen geven van hoe dicht het netwerk bij zijn capaciteitslimiet ligt. De tweede methode is een slim algoritme voor sensorplaatsing dat erop gericht is om onzekerheid (als gevolg van onzekerheden in de invoergegevens voor simulatietools) in de drukwaarden van het gasnetwerkmodel te verminderen. Het algoritme is in staat om de optimale druksensorlocaties te vinden voor minimale model geïnduceerde fouten in de drukwaarden.

Er werden twee onderzoeksvragen beantwoord:

1. Realtime meting is een vereiste voor controle: wat is de optimale locatie voor het plaatsen van flow- en druksensoren om het systeemgedrag te begrijpen?
2. Hoe kan de combinatie van monitoring, simulatie en regeling de werking van toekomstige gasnetwerken verbeteren?

Sensorplaatsing met de praktische regels die door de DSO's worden verstrekt en met het slimme sensorplaatsingsalgoritme, Astraia.

De activiteit richt zich op het vinden van de kritieke locaties voor druksensoren in het regionale netwerk van Uden-Boekel door de twee methoden te gebruiken en de resultaten mogelijk te combineren tot één optimale sensorplaatsing. Per definitie hebben de praktische regels en het slimme algoritme verschillende doelen. Daarom wordt een combinatie van de twee methoden voorgesteld.

Voor de huidige case studie wordt de prestatie van de drubbewaking uitgedrukt als de standaarddeviatie in de drukwaarden. De standaarddeviatie komt voort uit het simuleren van willekeurige consumptievariatiën en resulteert in onzekerheid in de gemonitorde drukwaarden. Simulaties werden uitgevoerd door TNO met Aurora, een gevalideerd gasnetwerkmodel dat nauwkeurig de druk, stroming en gaskwaliteit in gasnetten voorspelt. De resultaten van 1000 simulaties met willekeurige variaties waren de input voor Astraia, een optimalisatiealgoritme gekoppeld aan Aurora, dat de optimalisatie van 10 druksensorlocaties uitvoerde.

De simulaties en sensorplaatsing werden uitgevoerd op een deel van het 8-bar distributienetwerk dat wordt beheerd door Enexis. Het netwerk bestrijkt de gemeenten Uden en Boekel. Hier is een lijst met de scenario's voor plaatsing van 10 druksensoren (4 sensoren van praktische regels en 6 sensoren van optimaal sensoralgoritme).

Scenario's:

1. Basis scenario: 10 druksensoren worden alleen geplaatst met het optimale sensorplaatsingsalgoritme Astraia.
2. Praktische regel 1 en optimaal sensorplaatsingsalgoritme. Praktische regel 1 beschouwt de districtstations met de hoogste stroomsnelheden als kritieke locaties.

3. Praktische regel 2 en optimaal sensorplaatsingsalgoritme. Praktische regel 2 beschouwt de districtstations met de laagste druk als kritieke locaties.
4. Praktische regel 3 en optimaal sensorplaatsingsalgoritme. Praktische regel 3 beschouwt als kritieke locaties, de stations die het verst van de invoer verwijderd zijn. Voor deze regel werden de afstanden tot alle drie de invoeders geschat en onderzocht voor de implementatie van de regel.

Uiteindelijk worden de volgende conclusies getrokken:

Het effect van druksensoren die volgens de praktische regels zijn geplaatst, was iets lager dan bij Astraia.

Bij vergelijking van 4 druksensoren die door Astraia zijn geplaatst en de praktische regels, liet Astraia de grootste afname zien van de totale drukonzekerheid in het netwerk met 55%. Praktische regel 1 (DS met hoogste flow) liet een iets kleinere afname zien van de totale drukonzekerheid met een afname van 46%. Praktische regel 2 en 3 hebben respectievelijk een afname van 14% en 35%.

De combinatie van de methoden zou het meest gunstig moeten zijn voor de effectieve monitoring van het gasnetwerk.

Astraia was in staat om druksensoren die volgens een van de praktische regels zijn geplaatst, te gebruiken en extra locaties van druksensoren te vinden. De combinatie van praktische regels en Astraia had een vergelijkbare afname van de totale drukonzekerheid.

Afhankelijk van elke case kunnen de kritieke locaties die door de praktische regels worden gegeven, de minimale locaties met druksensoren zijn. De implementatie van Astraia en de plaatsing van extra druksensoren op optimale locaties, zorgt ervoor dat de uiteindelijke drukonzekerheid in het netwerk binnen de grenzen blijft.

Zonder druksensoren in het netwerk kan de onzekerheid in drukniveaus te hoog zijn voor een goede regeling van het netwerk.

Wat betreft de effectieve regeling van het druksetpoint bij de GOS in een gasnetwerk, moet er een gewenste druknauwkeurigheid zijn. In gebruikgevallen waarbij lokale invoeders zich op kleine afstand van elkaar bevinden, kan de minimale nauwkeurigheid voor regeling in de orde van grootte van 0,5 bar liggen. Daarom moet het netwerk met een gelijke of hogere nauwkeurigheid worden bewaakt. Dit betekent dat in het geval van Uden-Boekel de acceptabele drukonzekerheid aanzienlijk moet worden verminderd.

Algemene conclusie

Het regelen van de uitgangsdruk van een gedecentraliseerde waterstof invoeder vergroot de invoed capaciteit van deze invoeder. Om dit te kunnen doen moeten de drukken in het netwerk met een bepaalde nauwkeurigheid gemeten worden. Een combinatie van een gasnetwerksimulator en sensoren geeft meer inzicht in de drukken in het netwerk dan alleen een simulator of alleen sensoren. Het is aangetoond dat de onzekerheid in de drukken van het gasnetwerkmodel (als gevolg van onzekerheid in de afnamegegevens) kan worden gesimuleerd en verminderd door sensoren te gebruiken. De toepassing van praktische regels met Astraia kan de optimale druksensorlocaties vinden om acceptabele drukonzekerheidsniveaus te bereiken. Hierdoor kunnen de drukken van de invoeders actief worden geregeld, waardoor de totale invoed capaciteit toeneemt. En er minder snel moet worden afgeschakeld, of het netwerk moet worden voorzien van boosters om een surplus aan productie te kunnen managen.

1 Table of Contents

- Document summary 2
- Executive summary 3
- Samenvatting..... 5
- Abbreviation List..... 8
- 1 Introduction..... 9
 - 1.1 Background..... 10
 - 1.2 Research objectives and questions 10
- 2 Methodology 12
 - 2.1 Gas network simulation tool 12
 - 2.2 Optimal sensor placement algorithm..... 12
 - 2.3 Practical rules sensor placement..... 12
 - 2.4 Optimal sensor placement algorithm and practical rules combined 13
- 3 Case study..... 14
 - 3.1 Network description 14
 - 3.2 Worst case scenario 16
 - 3.3 Worst case simulation result 16
- 4 Sensor Placement..... 18
 - 4.1 Scenarios 18
 - 4.1.1 Base scenario..... 18
 - 4.1.2 Practical rule 1 19
 - 4.1.3 Practical rule 2 21
 - 4.1.4 Practical rule 3 22
 - 4.2 Discussion 24
 - 4.2.1 Base scenario..... 24
 - 4.2.2 Comparison of scenarios 25
- 5 Conclusions..... 28
- 6 References..... 31

Abbreviation List

Abbreviation	Description
DSO	Distribution System Operator (e.g. Stedin, Alliander, Enexis, Coteq)
TSO	Transmission System Operator (e.g. Gasunie)
GOS	Gas Ontvangst Station/Gas Receiving Station. A city gate station of natural gas from high pressure network to low pressure network with typical output pressure 8 bar.
OS	Overslag Station. Station with typical output pressure 4 bar.
DS	District Station. Station with typical output pressure 100 mbar.

1 Introduction

In the current low-pressure network, which is supplying a district with domestic and industrial consumers, natural gas is planned to be replaced by renewable equivalent gases. Currently, green gas is already replacing a small part of the natural gas in the grid. In the future it is planned that hydrogen grids will be realized. The research and developments within the HyDelta 3 programme are applicable to pure hydrogen networks.

By 2030, the goal set by the Climate Agreement [1] is to introduce 2 billion cubic meters of green gas. The green gas will directly replace part of natural gas supply and it will be a step towards reducing the CO₂ emissions. At the same time, the green gas feeders make the control of the grid more challenging for the DSOs. These challenges will further increase in the future with the transition to hydrogen. Since currently we don't have the hydrogen network, we can investigate the control strategies using the current natural gas network converted to pure hydrogen networks (e.g. scaling the demand by factor 3)

Currently, DSOs control most feed-in points with a constant pressure setpoint like a GOS station. In the HyDelta 2 work package 8 first report [2], it was first confirmed that DSOs have limited monitoring and controlling tools for the current natural gas networks. In the same study, it was concluded that the DSOs would be benefited with the introduction of clear and uniform protocols and criteria to determine the optimum locations for grid monitoring sensors and tracking pressure/flow variation in the network. In the HyDelta 2 work package 8 second report [3], the added value of an optimal sensor placement algorithm to reduce number of sensors needed in the grid was demonstrated. One aspect that was not included in that study, is that DSOs already have some experience-based rules for sensor placement in the critical points. These critical points are monitored to maintain the operating pressure within limits.

In the HyDelta 3 work package 4b first report [4], further aspects of digitalization in a future gas network with decentralized feed-in points were investigated. More specifically the control strategy of local hydrogen feeders was investigated. Some of the conclusions of this study were:

- Next to static gas network model for capacity calculation, a dynamic transient gas network model can help to compute pressure fluctuations (ramp-up and ramp-down) due to imbalance of supply and demand to determine the reaction time needed for balancing the system.
- In a network with multiple hydrogen feeding locations, the pressure management is quite complex. Especially when the total consumption is lower than total production during summer time.
- There are several ways to increase the capacity (uptime) of hydrogen feeder e.g. introduction of surface storage in the grid, implementation of booster station and pressure management of the feeders.
- A static setpoint pressure control can be used for feeder prioritization. However, it is not a straightforward solution when there are multiple feeders. A dynamic pressure control is a more sophisticated and effective solution, but requires more advanced technologies (real-time sensors, calculation model and remote control)

The general conclusion from all the previous work given above, is that the digitalization of the current gas network is required. It can be achieved by more advanced monitoring and controlling technologies. This report is the second deliverable of HyDelta 3 work package 4b that focus on monitoring of the grid, where the current tool for optimal sensor placement has been combined with the existing DSOs'

practical rules for sensor placement. In the frame of the HyDelta 3 research on controlling strategies, the scope of monitoring will be pressure sensors only.

1.1 Background

Current state-of-the-art of optimal sensor placement algorithm

Monitoring pressure, flow, and gas quality in the gas network are needed for network operation to guarantee security of supply. Sensors can't be placed everywhere due to the limitation of space and cost. Sensor placement problem has been studied extensively in water distribution networks (for leak detection or contaminant detection) [5] [6] [7] [8] [9] or in electrical grid (for power estimation or grid outages) [10] [11] [12] [13] [14]. However, not many studies investigate the optimal sensor placement in the gas network. We found two papers related to sensor placement in gas network. In this study [15], the goal of sensor placement is to monitor leak and water ingress in the gas grid by monitoring negative pressure wave and impact propagation. Five multi-objective optimization algorithms for sensor placement methods are investigated with the aim to identify the fastest method. In another paper [16], the flow sensor placement is investigated in the gas network of the island of Texel. The optimal sensor locations are found by minimizing the uncertainty of the flows from gas consumption data produced by a Monte Carlo approach. Our work is inspired by this study on how the gas simulation model is combined with sensors to have a more accurate prediction by reducing uncertainties.

Current state-of-the-art of practical rules sensor placement

Some DSOs have certain rules to determine where they should invest in implementing sensors for grid monitoring. Placing sensors in a gas grid enables the DSO operator to monitor the pressure in real time. Currently, the operators choose to place sensors at critical locations. These critical locations are identified from a list of rules that each DSO has. The purpose of the sensors is to monitor pressure at a single point. Based on these single point measurements and combined with years of experience and historical data, the DSOs can take actions to operate their gas distribution networks within operating limits and at the same time meet the demand.

1.2 Research objectives and questions

The proposal of HyDelta 3, specifically the work package 4b has defined the following questions:

1. What is the role of DSOs and the procedure for controlling the gas quantities from feeders into their grid?
2. What is the standard procedure to guarantee security of supply of the gas feeder?
3. What is the equipment system needed to monitor and control the gas feeder?
4. How to dynamically control the pressure at the gas feeder to increase the feed-in flow limit and increase the uptime of the gas feeder?
5. What is the strategy to control (multiple) gas feeder prioritization for balancing the gas grid?
6. How will the control algorithm be affected when there is more flexibility in the system due to storage, flexible demand, and intermittent supply?
7. Realtime measurement is a pre-requisite for control: what is the optimal location for placing flow and pressure sensors to understand the system behaviour?
8. How can the combination of monitoring, simulation and control improve the operation of future gas networks?

These research questions are divided into two reports. In the first report [4], questions 1 to 6 were investigated and answered. In this second report, questions 7 and 8 are considered. It is a continuation of the work carried out in [3], where the smart sensor algorithm was implemented for the first time in

a real use case of Kapelle municipality. In this study, the optimal sensor placement algorithm is combined with DSOs' practical rules.

2 Methodology

In order to be able to control the pressure of gas networks, a monitoring system is required. There are two approaches for monitoring the gas network: using pressure sensors or using pressure calculation from simulation model. The first method is accurate but requires a lot of sensors to have a large coverage and the second method has a large coverage but high uncertainties due to relying on good input data. This chapter shows how both methods can be combined and work complementary to each other for monitoring gas networks.

2.1 Gas network simulation tool

The gas network simulation tool Aurora is developed in-house by TNO [17]. This tool is used for computing pressure, flow and gas composition in both distribution gas grid or transportation grid. This tool has been validated to several real case networks in the Netherlands (Texel, Goeree-Overflakke, Kapelle) and compared to other commercial tools (IRENE pro, OLGA, Saint, Synergi Gas).

Gas network simulation tools can calculate the pressure and flow distribution in the whole topology grid with a given setpoint pressure at the GOS and a setpoint flow at feeders and consumers. The flow profile of each consumer is modelled using a combination of standard consumption profiles (e.g. G1A for gas meter G6 or smaller), weather profiles (temperature, wind speed, radiation, etc.) and standard annual consumption of gas. By running the gas network model continuously (i.e. with a time step of 5 minutes), the operator will have the pressure and flow for entire grid in real time.

2.2 Optimal sensor placement algorithm

Astraia is an optimal sensor placement algorithm developed by TNO for placing pressure [18], flow, and gas quality sensors [19]. This algorithm works in combination with a gas network simulation tool. The algorithm finds the optimal location and the minimum sensor needed in the gas grid by minimizing the prediction error of simulation tool due to uncertainty in the input data of the model. The pressure calculation can be improved by real-time measurement from pressure sensor.

The workflow for finding the optimal locations for pressure sensors involves the following steps:

- Scenarios: A base scenario, of a single time step is defined. Multiple scenarios with random variations on the gas demand are created. For each consumer in the network, the gas demand is increased or decreased by a percentage.
- Simulations: All the scenarios with random variations are simulated with Aurora.
- Processing results: The pressure results from the scenarios are processed. For every node, the variation of pressure is calculated. As a result, the standard deviation of the pressure is estimated for each node.
- Sensor placement algorithm: The processed result data are then further processed with Astraia. Based on the standard deviation of pressure on the nodes and on other parameters, the locations with the highest reduction of the total pressure uncertainty are found. For every sensor which is added to the network, the pressure uncertainties on the nodes are updated and the total pressure uncertainty is calculated.

More detailed information regarding this approach can be found in this report [3].

2.3 Practical rules sensor placement

Another approach for sensor placement is based on DSOs' knowledge from years of experiences in operating gas networks. This knowledge is put into practical rules with the purpose of placing sensors at critical locations in the network. Locations are identified as critical for various situations. Examples of situations where the operator needs to act:

- A part of the network has a pressure which is close to the upper pressure limit and increasing. This can happen if a local feeder is feeding gas in the network at times with low demand or when the feeder's pressure is higher than usual.
- A part of the network has a pressure which is close to the lower pressure limit and decreasing. This situation can occur if the demand is high with a combination of long distances of the demand from the supplier.
- Part of the distribution network cannot be supplied with hydrogen because of failure of a district station or a pipe. Especially if a part of the network is connected to the grid via one pipe or one district station, also referred to as an island grid.

The DSOs identify the critical situations and have formulated a set of rules for placing sensors in the network. Below the list of rules is given, as provided by Stedin with input from all partners:

- 1. Pressure sensor is installed at OS/DS station.** Due to pipeline being located underground and having limited of space, there is no inline pipe pressure measurement. Therefore, it is more practical to install the sensors at the stations.
- 2. Pressure sensor is installed at OS/DS station with high flow.** Station with flowrate larger than $XX \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$ is monitored by the sensor. There are no uniform XX flow criteria from each DSO. This station usually has a lot of connection to small consumers or connected to large consumers. Thus, it is critical.
- 3. Pressure sensor is installed at OS/DS station with the highest pressure drop.** The pressure drop calculation is computed by using the worst-case scenario, which refers to the coldest day with an outside temperature of average -13°C . On this coldest day the highest hourly consumption demand of the year occurred. The inlet pressure of this station is monitored to guarantee it is always higher than the minimum pressure limit (e.g. 4 bar for 8 bar network, different criteria for each DSO)
- 4. Pressure sensor is installed at OS/DS station with the longest distance from the GOS and local feeder.** This distance is calculated from the total pipe length between GOS and OS/DS station. This station is critical due to there being no other supply nearby. Additionally, longer distance means higher pressure drop.
- 5. Pressure sensor is installed at OS/DS station with an island grid connection with XX connection.** An island grid is defined as a part of network which is connected to single OS/DS station. Since there is no redundancy, thus it is critical to monitor this station. There are no uniform XX connection criteria from each DSO.

Note: At the moment the DSOs apply the rules differently for each distribution network. Therefore, depending on each network's unique characteristics some of these rules may be applied.

2.4 Optimal sensor placement algorithm and practical rules combined

In this study, the optimal sensor placement algorithm is enhanced with practical rules. This combination of two approaches will give a more robust approach to monitor the pressure of the network both from accuracy and criticality perspectives. The illustration of combined methods is shown in Figure 1. Pressure sensors are placed in the grid based on combined approaches. The real-time pressure measurement is used for the simulation model to improve the pressure distribution prediction in the grid. The real-time measurement also can be used from monitoring the pressure at critical locations. This pressure calculation later can be used to monitor and control the feed-in pressure.

Figure 1: Workflow integration optimal sensor algorithm and practical rules with gas simulation tool to calculate pressure in the grid with a reduced uncertainties.

3 Case study

The network for this case study is provided by Enexis and it is the same network as reported in the first report [4]. The Uden-Mill network is an interesting case for performing the sensor placement algorithm, as it combines characteristics like:

- Long pipelines that connect adjacent communities.
- Loop pipelines
- Multiple gas entry points
- Multiple gas exit points which are spread out in the network
- Local feeders with constant flow rate

These characteristics are found in many DSO grids in the Netherlands, therefore the findings from the current study are applicable to other cases. For this task, for speeding up the process of running multiple simulations for the sensor placement method, a part of the original network is considered. In the selected network, all of the key characteristics listed above are included

3.1 Network description

The selected network includes the municipalities of Uden and Boekel. The pipeline network is part of the 8 bar network from Enexis' jurisdiction. In Figure 2, the network of pipelines is illustrated with black lines, the GOS stations and hydrogen feeder are illustrated with green squares and the district stations (DS) with blue triangles.

The Enexis network is currently operated with natural gas. For the simulation model, the natural gas is assumed to be replaced with hydrogen, with a ratio of natural gas and hydrogen volumetric energy density (heat value) approximately equal to 3. Consequently, for the distribution of the same amounts of energy contents, the hydrogen flow is 3 times higher than the initial flow values with natural gas. Currently, it is assumed that the amount of energy use both for natural gas and hydrogen stay the same.

Figure 2: Uden-Boekel 8 bar pipeline network. With green squares are the supplier nodes and with blue triangles are the district stations, simulated as consumer nodes.

The areas of Uden and Boekel are supplied with hydrogen from GOS Uden and GOS Boekel respectively. Additionally, a local hydrogen feeder also supplies with hydrogen at the pipeline branch east side of Uden. Both GOS are pressure regulated with a setpoint of 8 bar and the local feeder is supplying at a constant hydrogen flow of 4500 Nm³/h. The selected network includes pipelines with a total length of 79 km and 151 DS stations where the hydrogen is distributed to the lower pressure levels grid. The parameters that describe the Uden-Boekel network are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Uden-Boekel network parameters. The demand flow rate is the total demand from the worst-case scenario.

#	Asset type	Asset name	Parameters
1	Supply	GOS Boekel	Pressure setpoint = 8 bar
2		GOS Uden	Pressure setpoint = 8 bar
3		Hydrogen feeder 1	Hydrogen flow setpoint = 4500 Nm ³ /h
4	Pipelines		1637 pipe sections Total length = 79 km
5	Demand (-13°C situation)		151 District Stations Total H2 flow = 81217 Nm ³ /h

3.2 Worst case scenario

The worst-case scenario refers to the coldest day of the year with an average day temperature around -13°C and it is called the “ -13°C situation”. The worst-case scenario is used by the DSOs to evaluate the robustness and capacity planning of the pipeline network. This condition is used to identify weaknesses and plan necessary upgrades to ensure a reliable gas supply under this condition.

The worst-case scenario in Uden-Boekel is adapted to hydrogen and it is simulated with Aurora. The results are considered for the rule-based sensor placement of pressure sensors. Specifically, we look at the pressure and flow results from the worst-case scenario and potential district stations are selected for every rule.

3.3 Worst case simulation result

Enexis provides the maximum flow demand of each DS station extracted from the Synergi Gas software. The total hydrogen flow demand of the 151 stations combined is $81217 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$. These values are used as input of Aurora to calculate pressure and flow distribution in the grid. The simulation results from Aurora then are plotted with QGIS, a software for visualizing map-based data. The flow rate and pressure results for the Uden-Boekel grid are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively.

Figure 3: Flow rate results in Nm^3/h , worst-case scenario simulation.

As expected, high flow rates are observed at the pipelines downstream of GOS Uden, GOS Boekel and Hydrogen feeder 1. The flow rates from these three suppliers are presented in Table 2. The sum of the flow rates coming from the suppliers is matching the total demand defined in Table 1 and it is $81217 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$.

Table 2: Flow rate distribution at the suppliers.

Supplier	Flow rate (Nm ³ /h)
GOS Uden	52820
GOS Boekel	23897
Hydrogen Feeder 1	4500

Figure 4: Pressure results in bar, worst-case scenario simulation.

As expected, pressure equal to 8 bar is observed at GOS Uden and GOS Boekel because these are pressure regulated stations with a setpoint of 8 bar. Pressure 7,77 bar is observed at the location of H2 feeder 1 since the injection of hydrogen increases the pressure locally. The lowest pressure is observed East of Boekel, with the minimum pressure at 6,79 bar.

4 Sensor Placement

4.1 Scenarios

A base case and three different scenarios are investigated in Task 3. As it was explained earlier, the current task is about combining the smart sensor placement algorithm with practical rules currently defined by the DSOs. The base case is defined as a scenario, where pressure sensors are placed in the network by implementing the optimal sensor placement algorithm. Then, three scenarios are examined. Each scenario is a combination of one practical rule and the smart sensor placement algorithm.

4.1.1 Base scenario

Scenario definition

For the implementation of the optimal sensor placement algorithm, a number of pre-processing steps are required. The first step was to define the network which was done with Section 3.1. The next step is to define the base scenario for the required simulations. The boundary conditions of the base scenario include the flow demand at the off takers of hydrogen which are the district stations, the pressure setpoints at the GOS Uden and Boekel and the flow setpoint of feeder 1. The setpoint values are given with Table 1. The only difference is that the consumer demand is not based on worst-case scenario, but it is based on winter year 2022.

The flow values were estimated by measurement values provided by Enexis. Measurements of flow rate for natural gas flows were provided for the year 2022. See [4] for a more detailed representation of the measured flow rate values for the Uden-Mill network. To arrive to hydrogen flow rate values for each district station the total flow demand was estimated by looking at an average winter demand. The average winter demand is represented by the average flow rate from the measurements of year 2022, all days at 9 am in December. The district stations have an average total flow of 45901 Nm³/h with standard deviation 34% (or 15000 Nm³/h) between day and night. We apply this uncertainty value as input of the simulation. The size and the locations of district stations is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Illustration of district station capacity. The 151 district stations are given blue triangles on the map. The size of the triangle shows the flow capacity of the station.

Results

The pressure sensor locations and the uncertainty on pressure comprise the results from each scenario analysis. The pressure uncertainty is calculated as the standard deviation of the pressure value on each node. The uncertainty is presented as the total value on all pipes in the network and as an average value per pipe. The average pressure uncertainty is the total uncertainty divided by the number of pipes.

Figure 6: Base case results. On the left, the total pressure uncertainty (top figure) and the average pressure uncertainty per pipe (bottom figure), are illustrated. On the right, the optimal pressure sensor locations are illustrated on the map of Uden-Boekel areas.

In Figure 6, on the right, a map with 10 pressure sensors optimally placed by Astraia is illustrated. Astraia found location 1 in the South-West part of the network, as the location with the most impact on total pressure uncertainty. At this pipeline branch and in the area nearby, a significant number of consumers are located. Additionally, location 2 is near the centre of Uden and location 3 on the pipe branch, East of Boekel.

On the left of Figure 6, the pressure uncertainty results are illustrated in plots. The biggest impact is obtained by placing the first sensor, which results in a total pressure uncertainty of 21,1 bar or a reduction of 19%. The second sensor at location 2, results in a total pressure uncertainty of 17,2 bar or a total reduction of 34%. The addition of more sensors, at locations 3-10 has progressively lower impact on reducing the pressure uncertainty. The decrease of uncertainty by each sensor is illustrated as the slope of the curves in Figure 6. A steeper curve represents a bigger decrease whereas a flatter curve represents a smaller decrease in pressure uncertainty.

The first 4 sensor locations can be compared with the sensors placed with the practical rules. Therefore, for comparison the total pressure uncertainty with 4 pressure sensors from the smart algorithm is 11,6 bar, with a 55% total reduction of uncertainty.

4.1.2 Practical rule 1

Scenario definition

The first practical rule is implemented considering the simulation results from the worst-case scenario, described in Section 3.2. Practical rule number 1 is about the flow rate at the district stations. The district stations with the highest flow rates are selected as possible pressure sensor locations.

For this rule, it is assumed station with flowrate > 3500 Nm³/h is critical to be monitored. There are four district stations fit into this category.

Results

Table 3: Stations with the highest flow rate. Flow rate values were simulated with worst case scenario.

Location	Flow (Nm ³ /h)
1	5375
2	4181
3	3889
4	3884

The highest flow rate values were observed in locations 1-4. The flow rate values are given with Table 3. The simulation results showed a flow rate of 5375 Nm³/h at the district station at location 1. The station is responsible for 11,7% of the total flow demand of the worst-case scenario.

Figure 7: Sensor placement results with practical rule 1 and smart sensor placement algorithm. On the left, the total pressure uncertainty (top figure) and the average pressure uncertainty per pipe (bottom figure), are illustrated. The decrease of uncertainty due to the rule-based sensor location is given with blue dotted line and the decrease of uncertainty due to the sensor locations from Astraia is given with a green line. On the right, the optimal pressure sensor locations are illustrated on the map of Uden-Boekel areas. The rule-based pressure sensor locations are given with blue, whereas the pressure sensor locations from the algorithm are given with green.

The pressure sensor locations from practical rule 1 combined with optimal sensor placement algorithm are illustrated with Figure 7. The sensor locations from practical rule 1 are at locations 1-4. The district stations with the highest flow demand are found outside of the centres of Uden and Boekel municipalities. Location 1 is on the West of Uden and location 2 is East of Boekel.

Astraia is used to find the effect of adding extra sensors, resulting in locations 5-10 to have the biggest impact on pressure uncertainty. Location 5 is at the center of Uden, near GOS Uden and location 6 is at the west of Boekel.

The impact of sensors at location 1-10 is given in the left part of Figure 7. With pressure sensors at locations 1-4, the total pressure uncertainty is 13,9 bar which relates to 46% total reduction in uncertainty.

4.1.3 Practical rule 2

Scenario definition

The second rule considers the pressure results from the worst-case scenario simulation. The most critical locations are district stations with the biggest pressure drop. The four stations from the simulation results are selected. These four stations are the possible locations for placing a pressure sensor.

Results

Table 4: Stations with the lowest pressure values. Pressure values were simulated with worst case scenario.

Location	Pressure (bar)	ΔP (bar)
1	6,793	1,207
2	6,873	1,127
3	6,878	1,122
4	6,919	1,081

The simulation pressure results for location 1-4 are given with Table 4. The GOS setpoints are at 8 bar, thus the pressure drop at the selected locations is in the range of 1,1-1,2 bar. The pressure difference between the GOS and the district stations occurs due to the flow through the pipelines diameter and the distance from the GOS to the district stations.

Figure 8: Sensor placement results with practical rule 2 and smart sensor placement algorithm. On the left, the total pressure uncertainty (top figure) and the average pressure uncertainty per pipe (bottom figure), are illustrated. The decrease of uncertainty due to the rule-based sensor location is given with blue dotted line and the decrease of uncertainty due to the sensor locations from Astraia is given with a green line. On the right, the optimal pressure sensor locations are illustrated on the map of Uden-Boekel areas. The rule-based pressure sensor locations are given with blue, whereas the pressure sensor locations from the algorithm are given with green.

In Figure 8, the sensors placed based on the practical rule 2 and the sensors placed with Astraia are illustrated, as well as the impact on total and average pressure uncertainty. Based on the worst-case simulation, pressure is lowest in the area East of Boekel. Therefore, pressure sensors 1-4 are placed in

the pipeline branches East of Boekel. More specifically, sensor locations 2-4 are placed on the same branch South-East of Boekel.

The additional pressure sensors placed by the Astraia algorithm, are evenly distributed in the rest of the Uden-Boekel network. The first pressure sensor placed by Astraia, at location 5, is at the branch on the South-West part of Boekel. Location 6 is centrally located in Uden.

The impact of placing pressure sensors on total and average pressure uncertainty is observed on Figure 8. Pressure sensors at locations 1-4 result to a total pressure uncertainty value of 22,37 bar with a 14% total reduction.

4.1.4 Practical rule 3

Scenario definition

The third rule is considering the distance between the suppliers and the stations. In an imaginary network where there is one supplier, the estimation of the possible sensor location is straight forward. The distances from all stations can be calculated and then the stations at the longest distances are selected. In the Uden-Boekel grid, there are three suppliers. GOS Uden, GOS Boekel and H2 feeder 1. To implement the rule in the current case, all three distances to the suppliers are considered.

Example

Figure 9: Example of the practical rule 3 implementation. In the example the distances from the district station in the North-East part of the network to GOS Uden, GOS Boekel and Hydrogen feeder 1 are examined. The blue path is the shortest distance from the station to H2 feeder 1, the red path is the shortest to GOS Uden and the green path is the shortest to GOS Boekel.

An example of how the practical rule 3 is implemented is given with Figure 9. In the example the station which is marked with a yellow star is considered. This station is located at a long distance from GOS Boekel (green path) and GOS Uden (red path). At the same time, the station is near H2 feeder 1, which makes this station not suitable for a pressure sensor based on practical rule 3.

To obtain the possible sensor locations, the shortest paths from each district station to GOS Uden, GOS Boekel and Hydrogen feeder 1 are calculated. The shortest path of the three is considered for the comparison. With this step, it is ensured that the reference path is the path to the closest supplier for each district station. A list with one reference path for each district station is therefore created. The district stations with the longest reference paths (shortest path to the nearest supplier) are selected as the possible sensor locations.

Results

Table 5: Result from the analysis of the shortest paths to suppliers. The column Reference path includes the shortest path from each row, the reference value is given with blue characters. Locations 1-4 have the longest reference paths in the Uden-Boekel network.

Location	Reference path (m)	Shortest path to GOS Uden (m)	Shortest path to GOS Boekel (m)	Shortest path to H2 feeder 1 (m)
1	5175	5175	5451	13072
2	4825	15149	4825	23045
3	4805	4805	13342	13376
4	4777	4777	13314	13348

The longest reference paths are given with Table 5.

Figure 10: Sensor placement results with practical rule 3 and smart sensor placement algorithm. On the left, the total pressure uncertainty (top figure) and the average pressure uncertainty per pipe (bottom figure), are illustrated. On the right, the optimal pressure sensor locations are illustrated on the map of Uden-Boekel areas. With blue, the rule-based pressure sensor locations are with, whereas the pressure sensor locations from the algorithm are given with green.

The selected locations for 10 pressure sensors and the impact on pressure uncertainty is given with Figure 10. Sensor locations defined by the practical rule 3 are in different areas of the network. Location 1 is near the middle of the pipeline that connects Uden and Boekel municipalities. Location 2 is on the South-East end of the network and locations 3 and 4 are on the North-West end of the network.

Additional sensor locations determined with the Astraia algorithm are again distributed in the network. Location 5 is on the branch, West of Boekel and location 6 is near the centre of Uden municipality.

Finally, the uncertainty decrease is observed on the plots from Figure 10. The addition of pressure sensors at locations 1-4 results in a total pressure uncertainty of 16,84 bar with a total reduction of 35%.

4.2 Discussion

In this section, the sensor location as well as the pressure uncertainty curves are compared for all scenarios. Additionally, the effect of sensor placement is visualized as a map.

4.2.1 Base scenario

The update pressure uncertainty values for every added sensor were calculated. The effect of sensors at location 1 and 2 compared to original situation is illustrated with Figure 11 below. The pressure uncertainty values are given with colour and the value per node is in the range 0-0,07 bar.

Figure 11: Effect of first and second pressure sensor on pressure uncertainty. On the left is the initial pressure uncertainty values, in the middle are the pressure uncertainty values with a pressure sensor at location 1 and on the right are the pressure uncertainty values with pressure sensors at location 1 and 2.

The sensor locations are found by the algorithm to have the biggest impact on total pressure uncertainty reduction. When we look into pressure uncertainty per node, on the left figure, the initial uncertainty is in the range 0-0,01 bar near GOS Uden, GOS Boekel and hydrogen feeder 1. The pressure uncertainty increases at the nodes which are far from the suppliers (or close to district stations). For example, in the pipeline branches on the West and East of Boekel, the pressure uncertainty is going to 0,07 bar.

By introducing the first pressure sensor, the pressure uncertainty values change to the values found in the middle of Figure 11. The most impact is found in the area around the sensor location 1, marked with the red circle. In the marked area, some nodes seem to have a pressure uncertainty decreased from approximately 0,07 to below 0,004 bar. The total pressure uncertainty is 21,1 bar, which is 19% lower than the initial value.

The second sensor has also a significant impact on pressure uncertainty reduction in the area around sensor location 2, which is marked with a red circle on Figure 11. With the second sensor, some nodes had a decreases of pressure uncertainty from approximately 0,02 to below 0,004 bar, near the sensor location. The total pressure uncertainty is 17,17 bar, which is 34% lower than the initial value.

Even though the affected area observed on the map in Figure 11 is larger, the total decrease of pressure uncertainty is smaller compared to sensor 1. The pressure uncertainty reduction for each added sensor and the pressure uncertainty reduction compared to the initial value are given below with Table 6.

Table 6: Results from smart sensor placement with Astraia. Total uncertainty results and decrease in percentage for the optimal sensor locations.

Number of sensors (-)	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Total pressure uncertainty (bar)	25.9	21.1	17.2	14.2	11.6	10.0	8.8	8.1	7.3	6.7	6.2
Improvement percentage for each added sensor (%)	-	-19%	-18%	-18%	-18%	-14%	-12%	-8%	-9%	-8%	-8%
Total pressure uncertainty reduction (%)	-	-19%	-34%	-45%	-55%	-61%	-66%	-69%	-72%	-74%	-76%

The decrease of total pressure uncertainty as well as the decrease in percentage of total uncertainty for the pressure sensor locations found with Astraia are given with Table 6. As it was also observed in Figure 6, the total pressure uncertainty value decreases with additional pressure sensors. The effect is larger for the first 4 sensors and smaller for sensors 5-10. This is reflected with by observing at the decrease as in a percentage value. The first 4 sensors have an uncertainty reduction between 18% - 19%, whereas the sensors 7-10 has a reduction between 8%-9%. The decreasing effect suggests that there is a clear trade-off between the number of sensors installed in the grid and the result total pressure uncertainty. On the one hand, the cost for the operator should increase linearly with the number of sensors. On the other hand, the gain on pressure accuracy decelerates, which means that that only a number of sensors have a significant gain. If, for example, 50% decrease on total pressure uncertainty is assumed as significant, then sensors 1-4 should be considered.

4.2.2 Comparison of scenarios

Pressure sensor locations

For both sensor placement methods, the possible sensor locations are the district stations. Therefore, there are 151 possible pressure sensor locations in the Uden-Boekel network. Out of these 151 locations, 11 were selected with the practical rules and 10 with the Astraia smart algorithm.

Figure 12: Comparison of pressure sensors placed by the practical rules (left) with the pressure sensors placed by the smart sensor placement algorithm Astraia (right). The numbers which are next to the sensor locations indicate the order of placement from each method (practical rule or smart sensor placement algorithm).

In Figure 12, the sensor locations found with the practical rules and Astraia are given in two plots. On the left, the locations from the practical rules are shown. 11 sensor locations are found with the practical rules and 10 locations with Astraia for comparison. The sensor locations in the left and right plot have one common location. For example, the location 1 from practical rule 3 is also the location 10 from Astraia. The results confirm that the objective of the practical rules and Astraia for placing pressure sensors is different, therefore the result locations are mostly different in priority.

A few sensor locations from the practical rules are close to each other. For example, the 4 locations from rule 2 are found in the same area, East of Boekel. Therefore, the placement of sensors 2-4 based on rule 2 is not providing of additional value. Sensor locations 1 or 2 are considered adequate to observe the lowest pressure in the network. Additionally, sensor locations 3 and 4 from practical rule 3, are also considered close to each other. Sensor location 2 from practical rule 3 can be covered by sensor location 2 from practical rule 2. In general, the implementation of the practical rule gives critical points in a network and the number of the sensors should be tailored to each case.

On the other hand, sensor locations from Astraia, are more evenly distributed in the network where sensor can decrease uncertainty the most. As it was observed in Figure 11, the most impact of a pressure sensor is found in the area where there is high flow demand or far away from GOS (the highest pressure drop).

Decrease of pressure uncertainty

Only the total pressure uncertainty values are discussed in this section for simplicity. The same conclusions can be drawn with normalize pressure uncertainty per pipe. For comparison purposes, the pressure uncertainty results are plotted and compared for the first four pressure sensors per method. The methods are the Astraia smart algorithm and the three practical rules.

Figure 13: Comparison of total pressure uncertainty in bar with four pressure sensors for each practical rule and the Astraia smart algorithm.

Figure 13 illustrates the initial total uncertainty in the network and the result total pressure uncertainty from the four methods of sensor placement investigated in the current report. It is observed that the initial value is decreased by 55% by Astraia method and 46 % by practical rule 1. Practical rule 2 and 3 had a decrease of 14% and 35% respectively. As can be seen in practical rule 1, high flowrates can have impact in uncertainty, thus it has similar results with Astraia. However, the priority could be different

due to the objectives of both methods (e.g. the first sensor of Astraia is the fourth sensor of practical rule 1, etc.). From this comparison, DSOs can have a better understanding what is the priority when placing the sensor since the results of both methods are in line. However, if we look into practical rule 2 result, the highest pressure drop station is good for monitoring critical location, but does not have big improvement in total uncertainty prediction from soft sensing (simulator) since there is only few district station nearby.

5 Conclusions

The results of the simulations were valuable for answering the research questions of this study. The first research question was about finding the optimal location of flow and pressure sensors in a hydrogen network. An investigation on the Uden-Boekel network proved that the Astraia smart algorithm and the practical rules provided by the DSOs can be implemented to find the optimal locations for pressure sensors. An equivalent workflow can be followed for the placement of flow sensors. In this study, the primary focus is on pressure sensor because it was shown in the previous report [4] that the prioritization decentralized hydrogen feed in can be controlled by using setpoint pressure. However, we need to have a better accuracy of pressure monitoring due to the bandwidth of setpoint pressure is small (within 0,5 bar) if there are multiple feeders next to each other. This accuracy is applicable both for natural gas network and hydrogen network with the same energy delivered (3 times more flows). Thus, hydrogen network will have similar pressure distributions / pressure drops with natural gas network.

The second research question was about combining monitoring, simulation, and control for improving the operational decisions of the future gas networks. The study results illustrated how the monitoring and simulation can complement each other for the operation of the network. These combination of two methods will lead a larger coverage of monitoring location in the network. Monitoring and simulation model are pre-requisites for the optimal control, which is a final tool that the gas network operators will need in the future, when hydrogen replaces natural gas.

Below is a list of the general conclusions and lessons learned from the current study in a combination with the first part of this work package [4].

The effect of sensors placed by practical rules and the smart sensor placement algorithm Astraia

The results of this study indicate that sensor locations placed by Astraia are the optimal locations for minimizing the pressure uncertainty in the grid. The pressure sensor locations were strategically spread in the Uden-Boekel network, in areas which combined high flow demands and pressure drops.

The effect of practical rules on pressure uncertainty reduction is overall lower which as expected since the goal is for monitoring critical location. However, the practical rule 1 where district stations with the highest flow rates had similar results with Astraia but having different placement priority (see Figure 12). For the practical rule, the stations with the highest flow rates were first on priority. The flow rates at each station were compared because high flow rate is an indication of many connections to gas consumers and an indication of high possibility of large pressure drop. For Astraia, the locations where the placement of the pressure sensor has the biggest impact on total pressure uncertainty, are highest on priority.

Combination of sensor locations from practical rules and smart algorithm for optimal operation

As it was illustrated, the critical locations can be found based on rules. In addition, Astraia can be implemented with a given starting point of sensor locations, to determine the location of additional pressure sensors. Combining pressure sensor locations from practical rules and from smart sensor placement algorithm is beneficial to both applications. The first application of the pressure sensors is for direct monitoring of critical locations. The second application is for predicting pressures in the network with simulations with desired pressure uncertainty.

The final pressure sensor placement should be decided based on how critical the sensor locations are and what is the desired monitoring accuracy. The criticality of parts of the network requires more

information to decide. For example, consumption patterns throughout the year, the interaction of the network to other pressure levels and more.

Maximum pressure uncertainty in the network for effective control of the pressure setpoints

From the results presented with Figure 11, the maximum pressure uncertainty found based on simulations of the Uden-Boekel network was 0,07 bar. The pressure uncertainty is the standard deviation from the pressure results, which means that standard deviations is also equal to $\sigma = 0.07 \text{ bar}$. Therefore, there is a 97.7% probability that the pressure value on one node is within the pressure range equal to $P_{mean} \pm 3\sigma$. As a result, based on a standard deviation of 0,07 bar, there will be at least a few nodes in the network where the pressure is varying by $\pm 0,21 \text{ bar}$. Please note that this uncertainty is from December 2022, it could lead to a different value for different months and year. The biggest impact on uncertainty values is expected during periods when the pressure variations are higher.

From the study in [4], on control strategies for decentralized hydrogen feed-in, a better accuracy was required. Specifically, it was reported that in scenarios where demand is lower than $14,4 \text{ kNm}^3/\text{h}$, the optimal pressure setpoints for allowing prioritization should be controlled within 0,5 bar. This accuracy is needed because there are 2 feeders located close each other. Consequently, the initial total pressure uncertainty and the required control accuracy are in the same order of magnitude. For the effective pressure setpoint control, additional sensors are required. The results with Astraia Figure 6, demonstrated that the average pressure uncertainty decreases by 50% with the optimal placement of 4 pressure sensors. With this level of accuracy, then the setpoint pressure of hydrogen feeder can be set with a small bandwidth.

To decrease the initial pressure uncertainty to meet the target uncertainty, 4 out of 151 or 2.6% district stations were selected for pressure sensor placement. Assuming the pressure variation is equal to $\pm 3\sigma$, the pressure variation decreases from $\pm 0.21 \text{ bar}$ to $\pm 0.09 \text{ bar}$ with 4 pressure sensors optimally placed by Astraia. Concluding, for the current case of Uden-Boekel network, requires at least 4 pressure sensors to reduce the pressure variation to the target order of magnitude of below 0.1 bar. These 4 sensor locations are also can be enhanced with additional 1-2 sensors determined by practical rules to monitor critical locations.

Concluding Remarks

This study is a research chain of the digitalization topic in the HyDelta programme. In HyDelta 2, a state of the art and technology readiness for future hydrogen DSO grids was investigated. It is concluded that monitoring, modelling and control is needed to enhance gas network operational excellences. Monitoring is a pre-requisite to control the gas network. Modelling tools can also give complementary insights next to monitoring. For monitoring, due to the fact it is infeasible to place sensors everywhere, a smart algorithm was demonstrated to place pressure and flow sensors based on optimal location and number of sensors.

The links to the HyDelta 2 reports are given below:

- [D8.1 & D8.2 State of the art technologies in the current gas grid and gap definition with the future hydrogen grid](#), also found in references as [2].
- [D8.3 & D8.4 Simulation of selected cases for digitalisation in a Dutch hydrogen distribution network](#), also found in references as [3].

In HyDelta 3, the dynamic pressure control was demonstrated with an advanced simulation tool. Due to oversupply of gas during summer time, prioritization of local feeders is needed. The prioritization is performed by controlling the pressure setpoints of the GOS stations and the local feeders. In order to do this, it is found that the setpoint pressure should have at least 0,1 bar accuracy between feeders.

The link to the first HyDelta 3 report is given below:

- [D4b.1 Controlling protocols and strategies for decentralized hydrogen feed-in](#), also found in references as [4].

In the current report, a complete strategy for pressure sensors placement is investigated. The optimization algorithm and the practical knowledge of the grid operators is combined to better define a strategy for sensor placement. This combined method leads to reduce uncertainties to an acceptable value for controlling the grid.

6 References

- [1] Klimaatakkkoord, “Klimaatakkord.nl,” 2020. [Online]. [Accessed 10 2024].
- [2] R. Octaviano, D. Palochis, J. Poort and H. Blokland, “D8.1 & D8.2 State of the art technologies in the current gas grid and gap definition with the future hydrogen grid,” HyDelta2, 2023.
- [3] R. Octaviano, D. Palochis, J. Poort and H. Blokland, “D8.3 & D8.4 Simulation of selected cases for digitalisation in a Dutch hydrogen distribution network,” HyDelta2, 2023.
- [4] R. Octaviano, D. Palochis, H. Blokland and H. Vlap, “D4b.1 Controlling protocols and strategies for decentralized hydrogen feed-in,” HyDelta3, 2024.
- [5] K. Diao, M. Emmerich, J. Lan, I. Yevseyeva and R. Sitzenfrei, “Sensor placement in water distribution networks using centrality-guided multi-objective optimisation,” *Journal of Hydroinformatics*, vol. 25, no. 6, p. 2291–2303, 2023.
- [6] M. Cheng and J. Li, “Optimal sensor placement for leak location in water distribution networks: A feature selection method combined with graph signal processing,” *Water Research*, vol. 242, 2023.
- [7] L. Romero-Ben, G. Cembrano, V. Puig and J. Blesa, “Model-free Sensor Placement for Water Distribution Networks using Genetic Algorithms and Clustering,” *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 55, no. 33, pp. 54-59, 2022.
- [8] Z. Hu, W. Chen, D. Shen, B. Chen, S. Ye and D. Tan, “Optimal sensor placement for contamination identification in water distribution system considering contamination probability variations,” *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, vol. 153, 2021.
- [9] M. V. Casillas, V. Puig, L. E. Garza-Castañón and A. Rosich, “Optimal sensor placement for leak location in water distribution networks using genetic algorithms,” in *IEEE Conference on Control and Fault-Tolerant Systems (SysTol)*, Nice, 2013.
- [10] B. Hooi, D. Eswaran, H. A. Son, A. Pandey, L. Pileggi and C. Faloutsos, “GridWatch: Sensor Placement and Anomaly Detection in the Electrical Grid: Recognizing Outstanding Ph.D. Research,” in *European Conference, ECML PKDD*, Dublin, 2018.
- [11] F. Fusco and J. C. Villumsen, “Sensor placement for optimal estimation in power distribution grids,” in *IEEE Power & Energy Society Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference (ISGT)*, Washington, 2015.
- [12] A. Mwangi, K. Sundsgaard, J. A. L. Vilaplana, K. V. Vilerá and G. Yang, “A System-Based Framework for Optimal Sensor Placement in Smart Grids,” in *IEEE Belgrade PowerTech*, Belgrade, 2023.
- [13] M. A. Abooshahab, M. Hovd and G. Valmorbida, “Optimal Sensor Placement for Partially Known Power System Dynamic Estimation,” in *IEEE PES ISGT Europe*, Espoo, 2021.

- [14] L. A. Smith and I. V. Hicks, “Optimal Sensor Placement in Power Grids: Power Domination, Set Covering, and the Neighborhoods of Zero Forcing Forts,” arXiv, 2020.
- [15] T. T. T. Zan, P. Gupta, M. Wang, J. Dauwels and A. Ukil, “Multi-Objective Optimal Sensor Placement for Low-Pressure Gas Distribution Networks,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 18, no. 16, pp. 6660 - 6668, 2018.
- [16] W. v. Westering and H. Hellendoorn, “Optimal sensor placement using gas distribution network models: A case study,” in *IEEE 12th International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control*, Taipei, 2015.
- [17] R. van der Linden, R. Octaviano, H. Blokland and T. Busking, “Security of Supply in Gas and Hybrid Energy Networks,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 792, 2021.
- [18] R. Octaviano, D. Palochis, J. Poort and H. Blokland, “Digitalization in the Dutch gas grid: optimal sensor placement for grid monitoring to enhance network management,” in *IGRC*, Banff, 2024.
- [19] J. Poort, R. Octaviano, H. Blokland and I. Pishbin, “Optimal gas quality sensor placement for hydrogen blending in natural gas grids,” in *Gastech*, Singapore, 2023.